

THE PROBLEM OF USE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: Pedagogical process aimed at ensuring all-round development of children in pre-school educational organizations is complex and at the same time colorful. To achieve the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to properly organize each type of activity in preschool educational organizations. The article analyzed the issue of using innovative educational methods in the process of preschool education.

Key words: innovations, modern technologies, education, educational process.

INTRODUCTION

To fulfill the order of social society by building an information society by increasing the creativity (creative potential) of the learner, his ability to communicate, the culture of learning, efficiency and quality at all stages of the educational process (the field of information technology, information education documents, users) and guarantees promising results when choosing optimal options in the development of similar processes. It is an active learning process.

Active education is a systematic pedagogical process that ensures the conscious and active participation, independence and creative abilities of the teacher and the learner in the educational process. The acquired knowledge and methods of action in the conditions of active education will be perfectly systematic in content, logically complete and suitable for use in various production situations. The following educational methods are mainly used:

discussion; engage in thinking; reinforcement on the board; implementation of various educational and professional games, etc. Activation of educational methods requires increased attention to the following educational laws.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In fact, modern pedagogical technologies not only increase the productivity of the educational process, but also increase the independent thinking skills of students. That is why introducing pedagogical innovations into the educational process, using pedagogical technologies in education, using various innovative methods and methods, and improving the quality of education have become an urgent topic today. It is known that today in the course of the lesson "Crossword", "Muzyorar", "Sinkwein", "Case study", "Insert", "BBB", "Venn diagram" ", "Brainstorming" and "Zig-zag" technologies are used to organize the educational process. In this article, we recommend several more innovative methods that serve to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the teaching process.

The economic power of each country, the rise in the level of social and spiritual life is determined by the competitiveness of the educational system and the development of science. Therefore, in the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority is to fundamentally improve the education sector, increase the quality of education, form a generation with intellectual potential, physical fitness, in-depth training of specific sciences, and training of qualified personnel for various sectors of the economy. were defined as tasks, and it was envisaged to create an educational system that could ultimately meet the requirements of today's era. As a result of reforms in the field, the management mechanism in the preschool education system was fundamentally improved, the non-state educational service provision system was reformed, the secondary special, vocational education system was revised, the quality of training of highly educated specialists was improved. improvement measures were strengthened, a two-level system of post-university education was

introduced. The traditional way of education, which believes that its main task is to provide a certain amount of knowledge, is completely insufficient to prepare young people who can live in a rapidly changing world. Because science and technology have developed to such an extent that now a person cannot keep even the most basic concepts in his memory.

Today, taking examples from foreign experiences, implementing them in practice with a creative approach, developing normative documents, teaching-methodical literature, teaching-methodical complexes in accordance with the needs of the times, leading preschool education organizations based on advanced foreign experience and the task of forming knowledge and skills related to the field of modern management and pedagogical technologies among specialists is included among the current issues.

Preschool education is the main link of continuous education. Previously, this system served only to create conditions for the social activities of parents working in various sectors of the national economy, but now the requirements for the work content of kindergartens have also been changed.

One of the main tasks is to prepare children to study at the school level. New programs have been developed, tested and implemented, which are closer to the school curricula, in the education of kindergarten students. Positive results were achieved by using these programs in the educational process in kindergartens.

Innovative educational technology is teaching and learning that includes new or qualitative improvement of existing methods and tools to increase the effectiveness of the educational process and create the best conditions for learning and educational activities. Methodology of organization of lim activities. current trends of socio-economic development of society. Innovations in education include complex activities aimed at the emergence of innovations in the field of education. These innovations can be methods and methods of organizing the educational process, resources used in the educational process, scientific theories

and concepts. Innovation develops through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge, some kind of discoveries, inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, in which instrumental and technological knowledge is developed that reflects the possibility of practical actions based on existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which later lead to the emergence of new technologies. Innovations also develop in the process of educational activities. In the course of the study, students develop theoretical and practical knowledge, which can later be used in various areas of practical life related to the creation of innovations. Innovative educational technologies are based on three main components: Modern, well-structured content, the basis of which is competence in professional activity that meets the current realities of business activity. content includes various multimedia materials transmitted through modern means of communication.

Almost all preschool education organizations in our country are equipped with modern computer and telecommunication technologies. This, in turn, requires educators to have a new approach to their work. The introduction of new technologies into the educational process does not force the educator to be squeezed by technical means, but changes his task and role through a new approach, turning the educational activity into a profession based on a more vibrant, creative and creative approach.

Application of modern, innovative teaching methods. Such methods should be aimed at developing the competences of a young specialist, involving students in active knowledge and practical activities, and showing initiative in the process of learning.

Passive assimilation of educational programs is excluded. Availability of modern infrastructure in the educational process. It should be based on informational, technological, organizational and communication components that

help to apply new forms and methods of education, in particular, distance education. The use of various innovative methods and methods, methods and game forms in the organization of the educational and knowledge process in development centers: conversation, story, show, reading fiction, reading encyclopedic literature, reviewing and discussing, explaining , discussion, watching video shows, watching computer presentations, creative activities, research, experiments, using the secrets of living and inanimate nature, etc., the development of the child is carried out not only in educational activities, but also in the way of play. During the play and cognitive activities of the children in the centers, the educator monitors the children's work, pays attention to how interesting, comfortable and safe the recommended materials are for the children. If necessary, the teacher completes or changes didactic materials. The educator ensures that all children in the group visit each center for five days. Expected results, problems, solutions based on observation and analysis, the educator records the progress of the children towards their goals at the end of each week, if so, the problems are determined by the personal work of the pedagogue and the children and their parents.

CONCLUSION

Thus, properly organized work in development centers allows each child to find what he likes, to believe in his strengths and abilities, to learn and understand relationships with adults and peers, and to develop their feelings. allows them and their behavior to be evaluated, and it is at the basis of this developing learning.

In education, innovative technologies are used based on the use of certain approaches in teaching, i.e. principles that include the requirements and goals that are the basis for the development of new technologies. All innovations in the pedagogical field are based on strict compliance with the current stage of social and economic development of society. Currently, they should be focused on the

development of students' independence, the formation of self-learning and self-development skills, and the conscious assimilation of educational programs, not mechanically.

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